

SciCoMove Workshop # 2 – Turin, 11 and 12 April 2022

Skull collections. Series, standardization and instruments

Program

Monday 11/04/2022 - Aula Magna, corso Massimo d'Azeglio 52, Torino

14.30 – 15.00 **Reception** of participants

15.00-17.45 **Visit** to the “Cesare Lombroso” Criminal Anthropology Museum and Human Anatomy Museum of the University of Turin

18.00 **Opening conference** – Christian Greco (director of the Egyptian Museum in Turin) *Exhibition on the “mummy room” of the Egyptian Museum.*

19.00 **Opening of the Fernando Bedoya's exhibition** “*The art of trepanning*”, Museum of Human Anatomy.

20.00 Dinner

Tuesday 12/04/2022 – Aula Magna, corso Massimo d'Azeglio 52, Torino

Morning - “Exhibition and research of human remains in the Museums of the University of Turin”

9.00 Greetings from the University Museal System President (Silvano Montaldo)

9.15 **Speeches** (about 15-20 minutes):

1) Giancarla Malerba, Cristina Cilli (University of Turin), *The craniological collection of the Human Anatomy Museum with focus on reference for anthropological and modern medical studies.*

2) Giacomo Giacobini (University of Turin), *The paleoanthropological collection (casts of skulls and burials).*

3) Roberta Genta (restaurator), *Information on the exhibits of the restored mummies of the MAET. Ethical implications.* Information sur les expositions des momies restaurées du MAET. Implications éthiques.

Discussion

10.30-10.45 Coffee break

4) Cristopher Heaney (University of Pennsylvania), *On Peruvian Mummies: Transatlantic Debates on Andean Embalming in the 19th century.*

5) Cristina Cilli, Silvano Montaldo (University of Turin), *The reconstruction of the craniological collection of the Lombroso Museum.*

6) Maria Teresa Milicia (University of Padova), *Collecting the “authentic” brigands' remains.*

Discussion

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101007579

12.30 Lunch

Afternoon - "Skull collections in the move: specimens, series and interpretations"

14.00 Speeches (about 15-20 minutes):

1) Franco Capozzi (Leuven and Turin University), *The transition from criminal anthropology to forensic psychopathology*.

2) Marina Sardi (Museo de La Plata), *What bones can tell us about collecting and curation practices*.

3) Laura Chazaro (Cinvestav, Mexico), *Anatomy collections in Mexico*.

4) Irina Podgorny (Conicet, Argentine) and Nathalie Richard (University of Le Mans), *Skulls on the move and the debate about prehistoric trepanation*.

Discussion and conclusion

16.00-16.15 Coffee break

16.15 -18.15 Meeting on digital exhibition (coord: Daniel Grana-Behrens)

20.00 Dinner

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